

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VALUE PERCEPTION AND FAMILY ENVIRONMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT The main aim of the study is to find out the relationship between value perception and family environment of high school students. The investigator used the survey method of research. The investigator has used simple random sampling technique. Ten schools in Sivagiri Taluk were randomly selected. In total the sample consists of 300 high school students from the schools of Sivagiri Taluk. The investigator used family environment scale and value perception scale. The Family Environment scale is prepared and validated by the investigator (2015). The value perception scale is prepared and developed by Amalraj and Sindhya (2008). The investigator used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyze the data. From the result of correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between the value perception and family environment of high school students. Value perception and family environment of high school students are positively correlated.

KEYWORDS : Value Perception, Family Environment, Correlation, high school students

INTRODUCTION

The childhood experiences has a big influence in building children personality. There are essential to realizing formation of self intact, which could not be achieved except by giving full freedom to the child and foster independence soul. To fulfill this, family environment has a very important role for children's education. Because of through this activities, a child will get a large influence. Good family environment will have a sense of love and mutual help, which based on the strong bond between families, and has a large contribution in build a child's personality. It can motivate children to develop themselves and improve their capabilities and potential. Meanwhile, when the family neglect their children, this condition give negative effects for a child personality. The loss sense of love and family causing bad result in education. They feel such neglected and abandoned, and hinder its ability to foster a sense of self-esteem that can benefit themselves and the community around it. The right education is education that provides direction achieved a varieties objectives and activities. Motivate children achieved its objectives and carry out various activities, to drive him to success as well as providing a sense of confidence in him. Moreover, it can also provides an opportunity for him to showcase his personality also meet physical needs, psychological needs, and social needs. Finally he was able to blend in and adapt to other people. Various research shows that training and educating children since childhood, giving a positive side to hone his personality and behavior. Like the wise people said: "Someone who seek knowledge since a child was like carve in a stone, and the person who study as mature was like those who wrote on water". Families are crucial partners in promoting positive social skills. Home visits, parent visitation to child care or school setting, telephone conversations, newsletters, informal notes, bulletin boards, workshops, and regular face-to-face communication can be used to keep families informed about the specific social skills being focused on in the early childhood setting and for care providers to learn about what families are doing at home. If guidance strategies are to be truly effective, parent involvement and support are crucial. Early care providers need to engage parents as soon as their child is enrolled in the program and ask for assistance in understanding the child's background and the family's goals for the child. Sensitivity to family and cultural differences is crucial and can be heightened by the care provider's ability to listen and encourage communication. Acceptance of differences in families is essential for each child and parent to feel a sense of belonging in early childhood programs. Mutual respect, cooperation, shared responsibility, and negotiation of differences in opinion between parents and care and education professionals are necessary to achieve shared goals related to the guidance and education of young children.

Mankind is passing through a crisis. The tremendous emphasis on the scientific and mechanical ways of life is fast reducing man to the

status of a machine. Moral and religious values are being undermined. The fundamental principles of civilization are being ignored. Conflicts of ideas, manners and habits are pervading the atmosphere. Disregard for everything old is the fashion of the day. At this situation, the solutions of all these social and global evils is through value education. Emphasis should be laid on such education through which moral values can be developed among the students so that they can conduct their life morally. They can decide what is right or wrong; what is good or evil; what is justice or injustice. If we can make a student as a good human being, the development of moral values within him is the prior task of education. They are the foundation of human existence. They make our life meaningful. Due to dearth of values in the present generation the curriculum must give prominence to value education. Value education has never been out of style. It is very relevant in almost all the fields concerning human activity. Value perception is a type of perception that has to do with the opinions and thoughts that students hold in regard to a values.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The perfect parental support enhances the behavioral development of the children. The parental support for children can expresses in many ways: Supportive parents can express their interest in children's activities, talk with them a good deal, take them on outings and games with them, provide help with everyday problems and school work, express enthusiasm and praise over their accomplishments and show affection and love. Children's behavioral development is affected by the environments in which they live. The good Home Environment depends on the perfect mother- father relationship. The uncontrollable growth of population, unemployment, violence, lack of responsibility and materialistic tendencies that we find among people area the other reasons for moral deterioration. The widespread indiscipline, falling standards, malpractices in examinations and lack of respect for the elders are some of the factors found everywhere. Knowledge is expanding but human personality is shrinking. To overcome this unsatisfactory condition, developing desirable values in the pupils is the only way. The Kothari Commission (1964-1d966) has rightly stated, " The expanding knowledge and the growing power which it places at the disposal of modern society, must therefore be combined with the strengthening and deepening of the sense of social desirable values is more important than giving more knowledge. The inseparable link between education and values is evident in the nature and aim of education. A life without values is an empty life. If it is the business of education to impart an integrated view of life, and if education has relationship with the meaning of life, then proper Value Perception of education becomes imperative. Values provide the underlying meanings that give continuity; to decisions and actions. Erosion of values leads to destruction of our nation. The erosion of

values leads to many ills that our society as a whole is suffering from today. There is erosion of social, moral, cultural, economic and political values at all lives. So value education is the need of the hour. As the Value Perception decides the success of the students in their life and becomes a foundation on which the society will be built. Normal family can decrease the chances of children becoming valued by creating a negative social dynamic within the family. If the family and school promote the Value Perception of all members of the community. So the investigator has decided to do a research on the title "Value Perception and Family Environment of High school students".

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

There is no significant relationship between value perception and family environment of high school students.

METHOD USED

The investigator used the survey method of research.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

In the present study the investigator has selected the high school studies in Sivagiri Taluk. The population for the study is IX and X standard students studying in the high schools of Sivagiri Taluk.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

The investigator has used simple random sampling technique. Ten schools in Sivagiri Taluk were randomly selected. In total the sample consists of 300 high school students from the schools of Sivagiri Taluk.

TOOLS USED

The investigator used home environment scale and value perception scale. The Family Environment scale is prepared and validated by the investigator (2015). The value perception scale is prepared and developed by Amalraj and Sindhya (2008).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The investigator used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyze the data.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

H0: 1 There is no significant relationship between value perception and family environment of high school students.

Table - 1 Pearson correlation test showing the relationship between value perception and family environment of high school students

Correlation	Coun t	Calcul ated " value	Table " value	Remarks at 5% level of significance
Relationship between value perception and family environment of high school students	300	0.345	0.139	S

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'r' value (0.345) is greater than the table value (0.139) for df (299) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant relationship between the value perception and family environment of high school students.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the result of correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between the value perception and family environment of high school students. Value perception and family environment of high school students are positively correlated. Values play an important role in the life of an individual and are the chief determinants of one's behaviour. It may be due to the fact that family influences one's values and behaviour throughout life and helps in the transmission of culture. Values inculcated during adolescence determine the personality of the individual. Hence, parents have a responsibility to ensure that values are inculcated in them. Both home and school have to play a significant role relevance with the value acquisition of adolescent children. Guiding the development of the child within the framework of human values is a shared endeavour. Family environment refers to all sorts of moral and ethical values and emotional, social and intellectual climate set up by the family members to contribute to the wholesome development of an individual. Family with its physical, intellectual and emotional aspects shape a child's life in his journey towards self-fulfilment. A powerful home environment

may be created for the child with the presentation of concepts such as ; the encouragement of incidental learning, freedom to reactions of the environment, scopes of the physical materials, attention from adults and the close relationship between parents and the child. A good parental bond with children allows them autonomy, independence, psychological and emotional space. The growing concern over the erosion of essential values and an increasing cynicism in society has brought to focus the need for value education in our educational system for adolescent students for the prosperity of our nation. The National Policy on Education (1992) has rightly emphasized that in our culturally plural society, education should foster universal and eternal values, oriented towards the unity and integration of our people. Value education is an instrument for social change and control.

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